

INTERACTIVE VISUALIZATION OF GEOGRAPHICAL DATA USING PROXMOX AND MODERN TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

This article presents an integrated system called ProxMox, an open-source platform that facilitates the centralized management of virtual machines and containers, thereby optimizing the processing, indexing, and visualization of geographic data. By utilizing Elasticsearch for indexing and Kibana for visualization, the system allows for the manipulation of data in GeoJSON and CSV formats, as well as the management of media files via FTP. ProxMox offers a scalable solution for managing geographic data, contributing to economic efficiency by reducing operational costs and improving decision-making processes.

Keywords: Economic efficiency, ProxMox, Elasticsearch, Kibana, Geographic data.

Scientific novelty. ProxMox introduces innovation in the economic domain by integrating functionalities for processing geographic data with indexing in Elasticsearch and visualization in Kibana. The system enables the automatic addition of geographic coordinates in tabular format and creates interactive visualizations, enhancing data analysis capabilities. Additionally, it offers the capability to manage and upload media files via FTP, all within a single integrated platform. This comprehensive approach streamlines data management processes, reduces operational costs, and improves decision-making efficiency, contributing to greater economic effectiveness.

Introduction. The architecture of the ProxMox system, integrating Elasticsearch, GeoJSON, Kibana-Web, and FTPImageVideo technologies, highlights the

effective collaboration of these components in processing and visualizing geospatial data. Designed to provide a scalable and extensible platform, ProxMox manages geospatial data stored in GeoJSON format, indexed by Elasticsearch for optimal search and filtering. KibanaWeb connects to Elasticsearch to retrieve and visualize this data, facilitating the creation of interactive graphical interfaces. Simultaneously, FTPImageVideo handles media files required for Kibana visualizations, ensuring efficient transfer between server and users. This description underscores the synergy between components and the economic benefits of ProxMox in managing and visualizing geospatial data. (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Data processing flow diagram in ProxMox

Source: developed by the authors

Kibana is used to create interactive graphical visualizations for data indexed in Elasticsearch [3, 6]. The FTP server manages connections for uploading and listing media files. Its integration into the ProxMox system allows for the efficient processing, indexing, and visualization of geographic data, combining all these components into a unified interface (Figure 1).

Modern geographic data management systems require efficient solutions for data processing, indexing, and visualization. ProxMox is designed to meet this need by integrating multiple technologies into a unified platform. By using Elasticsearch [1], Kibana [3, 6], and FTP, the system provides a comprehensive solution for handling geographic data, from geocoding to interactive visualization.

Methodology. This research employs a systematic methodology to integrate and assess the performance of the ProxMox system in conjunction with Elasticsearch, GeoJSON, KibanaWeb, and FTPImageVideo technologies for the processing and visualization of geospatial data. Data is collected and stored in GeoJSON format, which is then indexed using Elasticsearch to enable fast and efficient data retrieval. The integration of these technologies is evaluated for its economic impact, including processing time, labor costs, and productivity improvements.

Content. Modules described include the initialization of connections with **ElasticSearch**, indexing documents, performing searches, and creating new indices [1]. The practical example demonstrates how documents are indexed in ElasticSearch with data structured in JSON format. For instance:

```
python
Copy code
import elasticsearch
from elasticsearch import Elasticsearch

es = Elasticsearch([{'host': 'localhost', 'port':
9200}])
```

```
index_settings = {
    "settings": {
        "number_of_shards": 1,
        "number_of_replicas": 0
    },
    "mappings": {
        "properties": {
            "location": {
                "type": "geo_point"
            },
            "timestamp": {
                "type": "date"
            }
        }
    }
}

es.indices.create(index='geo_data', body=index_settings)
```

The Elasticsearch configuration specifies parameters such as "Host" for the server address and "Port" for connection. The number of shards and replicas affects data storage and redundancy. The types of indexed data include "geo_point" and "date," crucial for organizing and accessing information in ElasticSearch. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. ElasticSearch configurations

Source: developed by the authors

The **preprocessing interface** transforms GeoJSON data into GeoDataFrame and adds geographic coordinates to tabular data using geocoding. This preprocessing interface optimizes the quick and accurate transformation of addresses into geographic coordinates, reducing the time required for analysis or visualization. Accurate geocoding ensures data correctness in spatial analyses, and interoperability facilitates the integration of processed data with other geospatial datasets or analyses.

An example of using the GeoPandas library for this transformation is:

```
python
Copy code
import geopandas as gpd
```

```
from geopy.geocoders import Nominatim

geolocator = Nominatim(user_agent="geoapi")

def geocode(address):
    location = geolocator.geocode(address)
    return location.latitude, location.longitude

df = pd.read_csv("data.csv")
df['coordinates'] = df['address'].apply(geocode)

gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(df, geometry=gpd.points_from_xy(df.coordinates.apply(lambda x: x[1]), df.coordinates.apply(lambda x: x[0])))
```

In the spatial preprocessing process, GeoPandas plays a central role through its data loading and transformation functions. Initially, GeoJSON files are loaded and read using GeoPandas, allowing their conversion into GeoDataFrame for efficient and precise handling of spatial data. For geocoding, GeoPandas, along with Geopy, is used to add geographic coordi-

nates to tabular data, facilitating location-based analysis. For visualization, tools such as Matplotlib and Folium are employed to create graphical representations and interactive maps that enhance the understanding and interpretation of geocoded data within its spatial context. This integrated and efficient approach in spatial preprocessing significantly contributes to improved location-based analyses and visualizations (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Geospatial preprocessing process

Source: developed by the authors

KibanaWeb allows for the creation of interactive visualizations using the Kibana API [3, 6]. The Python-created graphical interface demonstrates the efficient use of automation in managing geospatial data visualizations, offering dynamic adaptability based on data changes. This approach enhances the efficiency of geospatial data analysis and interpretation in a professional environment.

The provided example shows how to create a Kibana dashboard using data indexed in Elasticsearch:

```
python
Copy code
import requests

kibana_host = 'http://localhost:5601'
headers = {'Content-Type': 'application/json',
'kbn-xsrf': 'true'}

dashboard_config = {
    "attributes": {
```

```
        "title": "Geo Data Dashboard",
        "hits": 0,
        "description": "",
        "panelsJSON": "[]",
        "optionsJSON": "{}",
        "version": 1
    }
}
response = requests.post(f'{kibana_host}/api/saved_objects/dashboard', headers=headers, json=dashboard_config)
print(response.json())
```

Kibana's functionalities include configuring and creating graphical interfaces through its own API, visualizing data indexed in Elasticsearch directly within Kibana dashboards, filtering and sorting data for precise views via the Kibana interface, and creating interactive graphical representations and maps using Kibana Visualize features (Table 1).

Table 1.

Kibana functionalities

Functionality	Description	API/Interface used
Creation of graphical interfaces	Configuring and creating graphical presentations	Kibana API
Data visualization	Visualizing data indexed in Elasticsearch	Kibana Dashboard
Data filtering	Filtering and sorting data for visualization	Kibana Interface
Interactive graphs	Creating interactive graphs and maps	Kibana Visualize

Source: developed by the authors

Using **FTP connection for images and video** in Python through the ftplib library, which allows for efficient and secure file transfer between systems. The provided code demonstrates a direct connection to a specific FTP server (ftp.example.com) using username

and password authentication. This facilitates the automation of the file transfer process, ensuring data security through secure authentication and efficient resource management.

The proposed code example shows how to connect via FTP and upload a file:

```
python
Copy code
from ftplib import FTP

ftp = FTP('ftp.example.com')
ftp.login(user='username', passwd='password')

filename = 'example.jpg'
with open(filename, 'rb') as file:
    ftp.storbinary(f'STOR {filename}', file)
```

```
ftp.quit()
```

The "Host" parameter specifies the address of the FTP server used for file transfer connections. The username ("Username") and password ("Password") are the necessary information for authenticating to this server, ensuring security and controlled access to FTP resources. The managed files include images and videos, indicating the types of files that can be transferred and managed through this FTP connection. These details are essential for the configuration and effective use of file transfers in an FTP environment.

Table 2.

FTP Configurations

Parameter	Value	Description
Host	ftp.example.com	FTP server address
Username	username	Username for authentication
Password	password	Password for authentication
Managed Files	Images, Video	Types of files managed

Source: developed by the authors

ProxMox is an open-source virtualization platform, ideal for implementing cloud infrastructure and hosting virtual servers. ProxMox combines a powerful KVM (Kernel-based Virtual Machine) hypervisor with an easy-to-use management tool [8]. This technology integrates all the components listed in Table 3 into a

single interface and provides high-level methods for data processing and indexing, creating visualizations, and uploading media files. The complete code includes configuring connections, transforming data, and creating visualizations, as shown in the examples above.

Table 3.

ProxMox components

Component	Functionality	Technologies used
KibanaWeb	Creating visualizations and dashboards	Kibana
ElasticSearch BD	Indexing and searching documents	ElasticSearch
Processing Interface	Data transformation and geocoding	GeoPandas, Geopy
FTP Images Video	Managing media files via FTP	ftplib

Source: developed by the authors

ProxMox represents a complex and dynamic virtualization platform, providing efficient solutions for managing IT infrastructure. Continuous development constantly brings new features and improvements, keeping it at the forefront of technology in the field. ProxMox benefits from active and ongoing development, allowing for the rapid integration of new features and optimizations. This continuous evolution ensures that the platform can successfully meet the increasingly complex requirements of users and IT environments.

Integration of ProxMox with emerging technologies, such as containerization, significantly expands the platform's capabilities, strengthening its position in the modern virtualization landscape.

The **economic efficiency** brought by the implementation of modern technologies is evident and is described in Table 4. The table is structured in two columns, presenting the advantages and disadvantages of each method.

Table 4.

Advantages (ProxMox) and Disadvantages (Traditional Method)	
Advantages (ProxMox)	Disadvantages (Traditional Method)
Processing Time	
- Optimization of processing time through the integration of modern technologies (ElasticSearch and Kibana), accelerating data indexing and visualization. - Reduction in time required for repetitive tasks such as geocoding and data transformation.	- Manual processing and data indexing are slower and more labor-intensive. - Data processing is slower and prone to errors without automation.
Labor costs	
- Automated technologies reduce the need for human resources for data processing and management. - Cost savings through increased efficiency and reduced work time.	- Manual processing requires more time and human resources, increasing labor costs. - Lack of advanced technologies leads to inefficient use of resources and increased operational costs.
Productivity	
- Increased productivity through the integration of functionalities and automation of processes. - Advanced visualization tools allow for faster data analysis and interpretation.	- Manual processes and lack of automation limit productivity, leading to delays and errors. - Data analysis is more difficult and slower without advanced visualization tools.
Scalability	
- Easy addition of resources and expansion of infrastructure as needs grow. - Rapid adaptation to changes in data volume and complexity.	- Difficulties in rapidly adapting to increasing data volume and changing requirements. - Lack of scalable solutions limits long-term efficient data management.
Overall efficiency	
- Integration of functionalities into a single platform improves operational efficiency and reduces data management complexity. - Interactive visualizations and advanced indexing allow for faster and more accurate data analysis.	- Fragmented processes and lack of automation contribute to reduced efficiency. - Manual analysis and lack of advanced tools can delay decision-making.

Source: developed by the authors

The advantages of ProxMox include reduced processing time, lower labor costs, increased productivity, easy scalability, and enhanced efficiency. In contrast, traditional methods are characterized by longer processing times, higher costs, lower productivity, limited scalability, and reduced efficiency. This clear and visual structure allows for a direct comparison, facilitating the understanding of the benefits of using ProxMox compared to traditional methods, and emphasizing the importance of adopting modern technologies in optimizing geospatial data management.

Conclusions. ProxMox's infrastructure is flexible and scalable for managing virtual servers and machines. The technologies of ElasticSearch, GeoJSON, and Kibana provide complex tools for data analysis and visualization, with FTP ensuring secure and efficient file transfers. ProxMox offers an excellent solution for businesses of all sizes, providing modern and innovative approaches to geographic data management.

The use of ProxMox in various economic sectors, such as urban planning, environmental protection, and transportation, can open new perspectives for users by enhancing the understanding of complex geographic data. ProxMox is recommended for organizations looking to improve decision-making processes and leverage the advantages of geospatial data analysis and visualization. Additionally, ProxMox offers benefits such as easy installation and configuration, efficient virtual machine management, robust backup and redundancy solutions, and straightforward updates, making it ideal for

complex IT infrastructures and environments requiring high availability.

Additionally, ProxMox offers further advantages through its virtualization platform, simple installation and configuration, efficient virtual machine management, robust backup and redundancy solutions, as well as straightforward updates and maintenance. This makes it highly recommended for complex IT infrastructures and environments with critical availability requirements. These features make ProxMox an ideal solution for efficient and secure IT resource management, providing flexibility and scalability to meet the diverse needs of users.

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